

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Efficacy of *Ipomoea batatas L.* anthocyanin in reducing mammary Malondialdehyde levels in female rats exposed to tobacco smoke

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Abstract

Objectives: Tobacco smoke is one source of free radicals that can enter the body through the respiratory tract and circulate through the bloodstream to reach all organs in the body. Purple sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas L.*) anthocyanin is a potentially powerful antioxidant that reduces free radicals. This study aims to demonstrate that purple sweet potato anthocyanin can reduce mammary gland malondialdehyde concentrations in female white rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) exposed to tobacco smoke.

Methods: This was experimental research with a randomized post-test control group. Thirty female white rats were used in this study. These samples were then divided into two control groups (negative control group - no exposure to tobacco smoke and anthocyanin; positive control group - exposure to tobacco smoke only -) and three exposure groups of exposure to cigarette smoke at a rate of two sticks/day and variety Anthocyanin doses for eight weeks. The malondialdehyde content of the mammary gland was measured spectrophotometrically.

Results: The result showed that the higher dose of *Ipomoea batatas L.* anthocyanin administered, the lower the MDA level in the breasts of rats exposed to cigarette smoke (ANOVA test, p-value = 0.002)

Conclusions: *Ipomoea batatas L.* anthocyanin can decrease the concentration of mammary gland malondialdehyde in female rats exposed to tobacco smoke.

Keywords: Anthocyanin; Malondialdehyde; Tobacco use; Reproductive health

1. Introduction

Many countries consider smoking to be a severe hazard to human health, including Indonesia. According to the 2021 Global Adult Tobacco Survey, about 70,2 million Indonesian adults used tobacco (smoked, smokeless or heated tobacco products) [1]. According to the 2013 Indonesian Baseline Health Survey 2013, 85.0% of Indonesian households are exposed to tobacco smoke, and about eight smokers died from active smoking. Passive smokers died from secondhand smoke [2]. Tobacco smoke includes oxidizing chemicals that can promote free radical production. Free radicals are

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reactive oxygen species in the body (ROS). ROS play a physiological role in the body under normal conditions. However, when ROS production increases, ROS and antioxidant imbalance can lead to oxidative stress [3, 4].

Exposure to cigarette smoke, one of the causes of oxidative stress, may be a risk factor for breast cancer. Chemical compounds in cigarette smoke can quickly enter the lungs when inhaled. Inhaled chemical compounds reach the blood vessels and then move with the blood circulation to the tissues in all parts of the body [5]. Free radicals from tobacco smoke, which are highly reactive, can react with phospholipids in cell membranes. The lipid peroxidation process produces a metabolite called malondialdehyde (MDA), which can be measured as an indicator of cell damage [6, 7]. Excess free radicals in the body are neutralized by free radicals known as antioxidants scavenger enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase and/or glutathione peroxidase. However, if the proportion of free radicals is higher, oxidative stress cannot be avoided [6].

Anthocyanins are one bioactive substance that can be used as an antioxidant against free radicals. Anthocyanins donate electrons to free radicals and can also increase antioxidant activity (scavenger enzyme) in the body to neutralize free radicals [8–10]. Based on the foregoing, the purpose of this study is to illustrate the effect of purple sweet potato anthocyanins on MDA levels in a female rat's breast exposed to cigarette smoke.

2. Materials and methods

The research design used in this study was an experimental laboratory with a randomized, post-test-only method. The study was conducted from June to August 2016 at the Laboratory of Pharmacology and Laboratory of Physiology, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Brawijaya, Malang,

The study's test animal was a female white rat, *Rattus norvegicus* strain Wistar. The test animals were fed and hydrated as needed, the rats were housed in cages 20x30x40 cm. We utilized 30 rats that were 1.5-2 months old and weighed 150-200 grams. Within a week, test animals adjust to their surroundings. In addition, the test animals were divided randomly into five groups, each consisting of six rats. The control groups were as a positive control group exposed to tobacco smoke (two sticks/day) for eight weeks without anthocyanin and negative control group not exposed to tobacco smoke and without anthocyanin. Others groups (three groups) were exposed to tobacco smoke (two sticks/day) with doses anthocyanins of 20 mg/kgBW/day, 40 mg/kgBW/day, and 80 mg/kgBW/day orally by gavage for eight weeks.

Test animals were exposed to cigarette smoke at the Laboratory of Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Brawijaya. Test animals were exposed to tobacco smoke for eight weeks when two cigarettes per day (each cigarette \pm 4 minutes) were given in the morning (1 stick) and in the afternoon (1 stick) via smoke pump [11]. Gudang Garam Kretek Cigarettes, a well-known Indonesian cigarette brand popular among locals, were utilized.

Purple sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas* L.) anthocyanins were used in this study. It was produced using modified flash column chromatography with a stationary phase of polyamide CC-6 and mobile phases of water and ethanol. It was done at the Chemical Laboratory, Faculty of Mathematics and Science, Bandung Institute of Technology [12].

After eight weeks of treatment, rats were anesthetized with 1% ketamine. Intramuscular injection of 0.9 mL of distilled water and 0.1 mL of ketamine. Then waited until the rats ceased to move. In addition, The experimental animal was positioned on the table with its stomach up. Tapes affixed to the soles of the rats' four paws were used to secure them to the table. The next surgery is then performed to take the rat's breast tissue. The breast tissue is then stored in a container to examine MDA levels further. MDA in breast tissue was determined using a BIOXYTECH MDA-586™ malondialdehyde spectrophotometric test. Up to 200-300 mg of breast tissue was homogenized by chopping and grinding in a mortar and pestle, adding 1 ml of PBS, and then centrifuged at 6000 rpm for five minutes in an Evendorf. The prepared, coded test tube was then filled with 200 μ L of sample or standard and 640 μ L of reagent solution R1, followed by 10 L of probucol. It was vortexed until homogenous and incubated at 45 °C for 60 minutes before being centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes to get a clear supernatant, which was transferred to a cuvette. The resultant supernatant was then spectrophotometrically analyzed at 586 nm.

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 1 Breast MDA Levels of *Rattus norvegicus* Average in all experimental Group (µM)

3.1. Information

Diffelrelnot notation (a,b) indicates a significant meaning (p -value <0.05), and if the notation contains the same letter indicates there is no significant difference (p -value >0.05) *post hoc LSD test*. Control (-): rats without exposure to cigarette smoke and Anthocyanin. Control (+): rats exposed to 2 sticks/day of cigarette smoke but without Anthocyanin, Treatment I: administration of anthocyanin dosel of 20 mg/kgBW/day to rats exposed to two sticks/day of cigarette smoke, Trelatmelnt II: administration of anthocyanin dosel of 40 mg/kgBW/day to rats exposed to cigarette smoke two cigarettes/day, Trelatmelnt III: administration of anthocyanin dosel of 80 mg/kgBW/day to rats exposed to cigarette smoke two sticks/day.

Tobacco smoke inhaled by the body then becomes free radicals, which are very dangerous for the body because they can cause oxidative stress conditions, cause cell damage, and trigger a malignant tumor [6]. The human body produces antioxidants to combat the reactivity of free radicals. Because these antioxidants trap free radicals and prevent their reactivity from interrupting by breaking the chain reaction of free radicals with cellular components, they are also known as free radicals. The parts of cigarette smoke that enter the body and lungs then enter the blood vessels and travel with the bloodstream to the tissues of all body parts, including the breasts [5]. The accumulation of free radicals, which is relatively large, can lead to an increase in lipid peroxide, which also increases MDA levels. Therefore, a high concentration of MDA indicates a high level of free radicals in the body [11, 13]

The results showed that exposure to tobacco smoke could induce oxidative stress in the breasts of female rats. It was marked by a significant increase in the breast of female rats, which was a significant increase in the mammary MDA level compared to the negative control group not exposed to cigarette smoke (p -value <0.05). Cigarette smoke, an exogenous free radical that may enter the circulation and affect all body cells and tissues, can induce a rise in breast MDA. Cigarette smoke contains a high concentration of free radicals, which increases intracellular ROS concentration. The action and elevation of ROS cause oxidative stress, which destroys lipids, proteins, and DNA [14]. In DNA, malondialdehyde can bind to deoxyadenosine. It has the ability to generate mutant DNA in bodily cells. In this case, MDA may be regarded to have an effect on the carcinogenesis process [15].

MDA levels in the treatment group receiving purple sweet potato anthocyanins at three different doses were lower than the positive control group receiving no anthocyanins (p -value <0.05). The results of this study are consistent with those of other studies showing that anthocyanins can reduce oxidative stress conditions in the reproductive organs of male rats [12, 16]. This study also found that a 40 mg/kg body weight anthocyanin dosage might lower MDA levels in rats exposed to cigarette smoke.

This study shows that purple sweet potato anthocyanin can be a powerful antioxidant to prevent oxidative stress induced by cigarette smoke. Anthocyanins can act as antioxidants by reducing free radicals and scavenging free radicals by donating electrons to free radicals [9, 17, 18] Anthocyanin is a type of polyphenol among flavonoids that can directly or indirectly reduce oxidative damage by preventing the increase of free radicals in the body. Anthocyanin is a flavonoid and a polyphenol that acts as an antioxidant. As a strong antioxidant, anthocyanin can act as a reductant in the electron transfer reaction pathway by donating electrons to unpaired free radicals [19, 20]. Anthocyanins can also increase total

antioxidation capacity (T-AOC), which are enzymatic antioxidants (SOD and GSH-PX) in the body, and lower MDA levels so that oxidative stress would not occur in body organs [8, 21]. Further studies are needed to determine the lowest dose that can reduce malondialdehyde concentrations in *Rattus norvegicus* exposed to tobacco smoke. Further research is needed to determine whether purple sweet potato anthocyanins may also affect carcinogenic compounds found in tobacco smoke.

4. Conclusion

The administration of purple sweet potato anthocyanins (*Ipomoea batatas* L) in doses of 20, 40, and 80 mg/kg/day can reduce levels of malondialdehyde (MDA) breast *Rattus norvegicus* females exposed to cigarettes smoke.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

This study has received ethical approval from the Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Brawijaya, Indonesia.

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